

In vitro study of the anti-coagulant activity of plant extracts

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: In the present study an attempt was done to identify anti coagulant activity of different extractions and compare the coagulation time .

Methods: The extracts of different plants like pineapple fruit, turmeric powder, cinnamon bark, and grape seeds are extracted by suitable methods and preliminary photochemical evaluation is performed to detect the presence of major bioactive compounds that are responsible for anti-coagulant activity .

Later invitro anticoagulant activity examined by using plasma combined with different extracts and using EDTA-plasma combination as standard and prolonged prothrombin activity(PT) of them was observed.

Results: In the observation 0.3 ml of pineapple fruit extract ,grape seed extract have shown prolonged PT than other extracts and standard sample.

Conclusion: All the plant extracts have shown anticoagulant activity, further investigation should be done to find out active molecules responsible for their pharmacological properties ..

Keywords: prothrombin activity(PT), pineapple fruit, turmeric powder, cinnamon bark, grape seeds.

INTRODUCTION

Haemostasis is a process of coagulation followed by anticoagulation, when there is injury in the vascular system. It contains majorly 3 steps: 1) vasoconstriction 2) formation of platelet plug 3) coagulation of blood followed by fibrinolysis hence the injury starts to heal. Anticoagulant drugs are used for short term & long-term treatment of arterial and venous thrombotic disorders and for prevention. Although heparin is used as an anticoagulant it has some limitations related to clinical applications, such as bleeding complications, heparin induced thrombocytopenia. To combat these complications, it is necessary to search for natural anticoagulant molecules. There are many medicinal plants which

show anticoagulant activity. plants are safer source of medicine hence, we undertook the anticoagulant study of ethanolic extract of *Curcuma longa* (turmeric), *Vitis vinifera* (grape seed), *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (cinnamon) and *Ananas comosus* (pine apple).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: Hydrogen peroxide, benzoic acid, ethanol, hexane, petroleum ether, acetone, Soxhlet apparatus, homogenizer, EDTA (ethylene diamine tetra acetic acid), sodium chloride, calcium chloride, test tubes, glass slides, syringes (5ml), cotton, spirit, micropipettes, turmeric, grape seeds, cinnamon, pine apple.

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Methods:**Preparation of plant extracts**

Aqueous extract of Ananas comosus: Fresh fruit is collected from local market and the pine apple was peeled and cut into small pieces. They are washed with 0.1% of hydrogen peroxide solution. Fresh juice is extracted and homogenized in the presence of sodium acetate buffer solution for 30 mins. 500 ml of filtrate is collected and 1gm of benzoic acid was added as preservative. The crude filtrate is a source of bromelain.

Ethanolic extract of curcuma longa: Freshly harvested rhizomes were collected, cleaned, dried and powdered. powder is packed as a thimble and placed in soxhlet apparatus. Now, the round bottomed flask is filled with 500ml of ethanol and fitted to soxhlet apparatus and further connected to condenser. Extraction is carried out for 6-8 hrs and the required amount of ethanol is added in between. Finally the extract consist of curcuminoids.

Ethanolic extract of Vitis vinifera seeds: Grapes are collected from local market and seeds are separated from pulp manually. The seeds are washed and dried at room temperature. The dried seeds are powdered. 20gms of powder is placed in thimble. 500ml of ethanol is placed in RBF and extraction was continued up to 12hrs. Required ethanol is added in between process. The extract is collected.

Ethanolic extract of Cinnamomum zeylanicum: 50gm of cinnamon bark is collected and grind into fine powder. cinnamon powder is extracted with 200 ml of ethanol and heated on water bath. Solvent is evaporated to dryness and extract is collected.

PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING:

All the extracts were screened for the presence of different phytoconstituents like alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, steroids, phenols, glycosides, coumarins etc.,

Figure no. 1 Phytochemical screening of extracts

Blood collection and plasma sample preparation:

Blood samples were collected from healthy volunteers of age 18 to 20 years. Blood is placed in separate containers containing EDTA to prevent clotting process. Further blood is subjected to centrifugation for 15mins at rate of 3000 rpm to separate the blood cells from plasma to obtain pure platelet plasma(ppp) for prothrombin time test.

Anticoagulation assay:

Collection of blood and plasma re-calcification:0.2 ml of plasma,0.1,0.2,0.3 ml of different plant extracts and 0.3ml of $CaCl_2$ are added together in clean fusion tube and incubated for $37^{\circ}C$ in water bath.for control the extract solution is replaced with same volume of 0.9% saline solution. The clotting time was recorded with stopwatch by tilting the fusion tubes for every 5 seconds. This is known as prothrombin time.

Figure no.2 anti-coagulant screening in fusion tube

RESULTS:

Table1: Determination of coagulation time:

Group	Name of plant extract	Amount of plasma(ml)	Amount of extract(ml)	$CaCl_2$ (ml)	Time of coagulation in min
Group 1	control	0.1	0.1	0.3	1.45
Group 2	Extract of pineapple	0.1	0.1	0.3	4.60
	Extract of pineapple	0.1	0.2	0.3	5.33
	Extract of pineapple	0.1	0.3	0.3	6.45
Group 3	Extract of turmeric	0.1	0.1	0.3	3.23
	Extract of turmeric	0.1	0.2	0.3	4.46
	Extract of turmeric	0.1	0.3	0.3	5.55
Group 4	Extract of grape seeds	0.1	0.1	0.3	5.25
	Extract of grape seeds	0.1	0.2	0.3	5.67
	Extract of grape seeds	0.1	0.3	0.3	6.66
Group 5	Extract of cinnamon	0.1	0.1	0.3	4.49
	Extract of cinnamon	0.1	0.2	0.3	5.46
	Extract of cinnamon	0.1	0.3	0.3	6.40

DISCUSSION:

The anticoagulant activities of all four pineapple, cinnamon, turmeric, grape seed extracts have shown significant anticoagulant properties. Hence, further identification and characterization of active molecules responsible for activity was to be found out in future. It requires further investigation to find out active molecules and their Pharmacological properties and other effects, among all the groups grape seed extract of 0.3ml as shown 6.66 minutes coagulation time and pine apple extract of 0.1ml as shown 6.45 minutes coagulation time when compared with other groups they have more anti-coagulant property.

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HOW TO CITE Siddhartha. Lolla, S.Srilatha, Aliveni patlolla, Sailaja avula,Saseendra madhupathi, In vitro study of the anti-coagulant activity of plant extracts, J. Pharm. Sci., 2026, 2 (4), 815-818. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19360238>

